

Functional Genomics for Plant Breeding

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Genomics is the study of an organism's genome, its genetic material, and how that information is applied. All living things, from single-celled bacteria, to multi-cellular plants, animals and humans, have a genome, and is made up of DNA.

The Plant Genome

The genome of plant cells comprises three parts

- Nuclear genome
- Chloroplasts genome and
- Mitochondrial genome

It is formed during evolution via the capture of proteobacteria and cyanobacteria by ancestors of eukaryotes and their subsequent adaptation as endosymbionts.

Plant Nuclear Genome

- It is organized into chromosomes that provide the structure for the genetic linkage groups and allow replication, transcription and transmission of the hereditary information.
- Genome sizes in plants are diverse, from 63 to 1,49,000Mb

- The smallest genomes consist of mostly coding and regulatory DNA sequences present in low copy along with highly repeated rRNA genes and intergenic spacers, centromeric and telomeric repetitive DNA and some transposable elements.
- The larger genomes have similar numbers of genes, with abundant tandemly repeated sequence motifs, and transposable elements

Plant Mitochondrial Genome

- Plants possess mitochondrial genomes that are large and complex compared to animals.
- Animal mitochondrial genomes are about 16.5 kbp in length, whereas plant mitochondrial genomes range between 200-2,000 kb
- the additional DNA found in plant mitochondrial genomes consists of large introns, repeats and non-coding regions.
- It does not exist as large circular DNA molecules but mostly as a collection of linear DNA with combinations of smaller circular and branched molecules.

Plant Chloroplast Genome

- It comprises of a single circular molecule with a quadripartite structure that includes two copies of an IR region that separate large and small single-copy regions
- The chloroplast genome includes 120–130 genes, participating in photosynthesis, transcription, and translation
- chloroplast genome size varies between species, ranging from 107 kb (*Cathaya argyrophylla*) to 218 kb (*Pelargonium*), and is independent of nuclear genome size

The Plant gene

Evolution of Genomics

The following major milestones that have influenced the history of genomics

1953: James Watson and Francis Crick discover the double helix structure of DNA

1977: Frederick Sanger introduces a technique in DNA sequencing

1995: The first genome sequence of bacteria (*Haemophilus influenza*) has been completed.

2000: Full genome sequence of the *Drosophila melanogaster* model organism (fruit fly).

2003: The Human Genome Project has been completed and confirms that some 20,000–25,000 genes are available to humans.

2018: On 17 August 2018, the IWGSC published a detailed description and review of the bread wheat genome reference sequence in the international journal *Science*, the world's most widely cultivated crop.

Genomics in Crop Plants

- Plant genomics work began in December 2000 with the publication of the entire genome sequence of the *Arabidopsis thaliana* model plant species.
- It resulted in a significant improvement in our understanding of the molecular basis of both plant growth and environmental stimulus response.
- Having the genome sequence enabled genomic approaches aimed at assigning a function to each of the 26,000 genes that were predicted.
- Knockout mutation generated by RNAi technique insertion mutagenesis or gene silencing indicates a role for a gene if it is possible to link the mutants to phenotype.

Further significant developments include

- the August 2005 release of a high-quality rice genome sequence
- September 2006 draft poplar genome
- 2007 full genome sequence of two grapevine genotypes
- 2008 transgenic papaya and
- 2018 full wheat genome.

Classification of Genomics

The genomics discipline consists of three sections

- Structural Genomics
- Comparative Genomics
- Functional Genomics

Structural Genomics

- It deals with the study of the structure of entire genome of a living organism.
- It deals with the study of the genetic structure of each chromosome of the genome.
- It specifies the size of a species genome in [Mb] mega-bases as well as the genes found in a species entire genome.
- It focuses on building genomic sequence data, finding and locating gene and building gene maps.
- It uses DNA Sequencing technology and program software to produce, store and analyze information about the genomic sequence.

Comparative Genomics

- It is a biological research field in which the genome sequences of different organisms are compared
- By comparing the genomic sequences of different organisms, researchers can explain what distinguishes different forms of life from each other at the molecular level.
- Comparative genomics also provides a powerful tool for researching evolutionary changes among organisms, helping to recognize retained or common genes among species, as well as genes that give unique characteristics to each organism.
- This compares the sequences of genes to explain the relationship is functional or evolutionary.
- It is a promising method for species with largely unexplored genomes to gain information by using conservation among closely related plant species

Functional Genomics

- It is involved in the research of the function of all genes found in the entire genome.
- This deals with the proteome and transcriptome.
- The transcriptome refers to a complete set of genome-transcribed RNAs and refers to a complete set of genome-encoded proteins.
- Functions must be allocated to all genes in the series after genome sequencing is annotated.
- Some of the genes may already allocate functions using a conventional method Mutagenesis and linkage mapping.
- Functional approaches to genomics use methodologies based on sequence or hybridization.
- Expressed Sequence Tags (ESTs), Serial Analysis of Gene Expression (SAGE) and Massively Parallel Signature Sequencing (MPSS) are analyzed sequence-based approaches.
- Hybridization-based approaches are array-based techniques that use target DNA hybridization with cDNA or oligonucleotide samples attached to a surface for expression assessment.
- The array-based approaches are targeted; that is prior transcript information to be studied, either sequence or clones, is a prerequisite for designing samples.
- Targeting Induced Local Lesions In Genomes (TILLING) primarily allows high-throughput analysis of large numbers of mutants, a modified technique, called Eco

TILLING, has been developed to detect natural polymorphisms, similar to TILLING-assisted induced mutation detection.

- Editing of TDNA, RNAi and Genome editing also used to assign Gene function.

There are several specific functional genomics approaches

- DNA level (genomics and epigenomics)
- RNA level (transcriptomics)
- Protein level (proteomics)
- Metabolite level (metabolomics)

Why functional genomics?

- Global climate changes and rapidly increasing population have been making sustainable supplies of food and energy unprecedented challenging.

- Superior traits such as better yield, abiotic and biotic stress tolerance, better water and nitrogen use efficiency and better food processing and nutritional qualities are of greater need.
- Cereal crops have been domesticated and bred as the staple food for global population for hundreds to thousands of years.
- Omics technologies (including genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, metabolomics and epigenomics), their increasing accessibility and decreasing costs enable the applications of omics technologies in plant sciences, and hence expand our knowledge in both model and non-model plant species
- Combination of molecular genetics approaches and omics technologies lead to rapid development in the fields of functional genomics, which have helped to unveil the functions of different types genetic components (such as genes, regulatory elements and non-coding RNAs), and laid solid foundations for crop genetic improvement.

Role of Genomics in Crop Improvement

Genomics has a range of practical uses to boost crops. In a number of ways, genome mapping is useful. It is useful or provides information on genome size, gene number, gene mapping, gene sequencing, crop plant evolution, gene cloning, DNA marker recognition, marker assisted selection, transgenic breeding, linkage map creation and QTL mapping.

- i. Genome size: Genome mapping is a very useful technique for assessing the size of the genome in different species of plants. The largest genome size was recorded in Wheat (14.5 Gb) and the smallest in *Arabidopsis thaliana* (120 Mb) in the plant species studied so far.
- ii. Gene Number: Genome mapping provides information on a species ' gene number. The maximum number of genes reported in Wheat that is 107,891 was reported in crop plants studied so far.
- iii. Gene mapping: Genome research is very useful in mapping / tagging genes on a genome's different chromosomes. In other words, it helps to discover new genes in a genome on a large scale.
- iv. Gene Sequencing: Genome mapping helps to establish the chromosome gene order. The gene order is determined on each genome chromosome.
- v. Evolution: Genome mapping provides information on various organisms ' evolution. This tests the interaction between different genomes and thus provides information on crop plants ' association or evolutionary biology.

- vi. Gene Cloning: Genome research is very useful in making multiple gene copies and moving the same from genotype to genotype. It therefore assists in the precise transfer of genes.
- vii. DNA marker identification: genome mapping techniques are useful to classify DNA markers that can be used in molecular breeding, i.e. marker assisted selection. From the mapping groups, For DNA markers, inter-specific crosses are extremely polymorphic than those representing populations resulting from intra-specific crosses.
- viii. Marker Assisted Selection: Marker Assisted Selection refers to indirect selection based on the band pattern of related DNA markers for a specific phenotype. Using such selection, crop improvement is called molecular breeding. Similar DNA markers used for this purpose are RFLP, AFLP, SSR, etc. DNA marker results are associated with morphological markers and then it's picked for a particular characteristic. Selection based on DNA markers is more effective because environmental factors do not affect DNA markers.
- ix. Transgenic breeding: In gene cloning, genome mapping is important. The gene of interest can be cloned and used in the development of transgenic plants. Transgenic breeding enables the direct transfer of genes bypassing the sexual cycle.
- x. Linkage maps construction: Genome mapping helps to create linkage classes. Based on gene mapping and gene sequencing details, the linkage groups can be constructed.
- xi. QTL Mapping: The techniques of genome mapping are commonly used for quantitative trait loci (QTL) mapping. Through conventional methods, i.e. recombination mapping and deletion mapping techniques, mapping of QTL or polygenic traits is not feasible.

The availability of a crop's entire genome sequence is very useful for plant breeding, given the high cost of sequencing the entire genome; transcriptome sequencing was a cheaper alternative. The cDNA sequences (expressed sequence tags, ESTs) provide relevant information on the genes expressed in a particular tissue or organ, at a particular stage of development and under specific environmental conditions. With the advent of NGS technologies, the genomics landscape has shifted. Such new technologies have lowered sequencing costs by more than 1,000 times compared to Sanger technology, reducing time consuming and repetitive Modern steps in cloning and allowing millions of simultaneous sequencing reactions.

Marker Assisted Selection

Marker assisted selection (MAS) is an indirect process where selection is carried out on the basis of a marker instead of the trait itself. The probability of recombination, given the close relation between the marker and the gene, restricts the use of MAS. Using intragenic markers can help to overcome this limitation, also called functional markers. Projects for NGS sequencing produce large sets of usable markers. Such markers boost the actual gene supported reproduction, thus reducing the risk of loss of desirable feature of recombination.

Conclusions

Genomic methods and strategies will help conventional breeding make significant progress in crop breeding that has either remained orphaned or ignored from the point of view of genetic improvement. Thus, though traditional plant breeding pre-genomics has been, is and will be effective in improving our crops, the application of genomic tools and resources to realistic plant breeding will drive forward the genetic gains obtained through breeding programs.